

PEDAGOGICAL APPROACH TO THE EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM

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Abstract: In this article, there are opinions about the scientific-methodical analysis of the pedagogical approach to the education and training system in the pedagogical process.

Keywords: Approaches to education, research-creative approach, pedagogical activity, educational technology, educational model.

In the science and practice of pedagogy, authoritarian and person-oriented approaches are used according to the nature of the attitude of different educators and learners. Traditional, research, research, systematic, functional, complex, technological, problem-element, activity approaches are distinguished based on the used educational methods and organizational forms.

The traditional approach is characterized by oral-visual teaching methods, which are mainly determined by the teacher's information, students' acceptance, collection and memory of knowledge. The concept of "knowledge" is understood as information stored in memory. Such knowledge is tested by re-presenting it and applying it to typical situations (depending on the answer to a question about this information in the exam).

Knowledge in this approach is mainly the result of memorization and consists mainly of formal information, which can often be superficial. They are stored in the depths of memory, or in other words, they are recalled only when a direct question is asked. Knowledge at the level of recall is not stored in memory for a long time. A student may remember a question when asked, and sometimes he may not remember it at all.

The oral-visual approach is widespread in educational institutions of our republic. It arises from the opportunity to directly provide ready-made knowledge to "teacher-students" in the information system, regardless of their needs and level of activity. Therefore, the main task of the teacher is to communicate the necessary information and work on consolidating it in memory.

According to V. Guzeyev, the characteristic feature of the traditional methodology is characterized by a kind of vague imagination wrapped in the concept of "mastering" the educational goals expressed in the program requirements. In this case, educational processes are organized based on the generalization of work experiences of teachers who have achieved more success in the educational process. For each specific situation, an example of the pedagogical activity of advanced teachers (pedagogues) is sought, but a number of scientists and practitioners working in the educational system believe that the era of separate methodologies has passed, and the generalization of the experiences of any advanced pedagogues is systematic and they seriously emphasize that it does not allow building goal-oriented, effective education.

A number of positive works in the field of education carried out in the republic, the rapid growth of science and technology, the training of competitive highly qualified personnel today, the development of the individual, and the needs of society in relation to ensuring a high level of his education. leading to conflicts between teaching styles. Therefore, it is important to use other approaches in the educational process.

Today, a new educational system aimed at entering the world education arena is being decided in Uzbekistan. Simultaneously with this process, significant changes are taking place in the theory and practice of the pedagogical process. The composition of approaches in education is changing and different relationships are being established. Forces with the ability to work with new information are being formed in the educational system, new creative solutions are being found, and efforts to individualize the educational program are increasing.

Education is an important part of the pedagogical process, and it is a person-oriented interaction between a student and a teacher (pedagogue). The role of science in the formation of pedagogical technologies equal to social knowledge is increasing.

The main directions of improvement of modern pedagogical technologies from the psychological and pedagogical point of view are expressed as follows:

- transition of the pupil-student from memorization to the function of remembering, i.e. transition to the process of mental development that allows to use what has been learned;
- transition from the associative statistical model of knowledge to dynamic structural systems of mental activity;
- transition from average student-student orientation to differentiated and individualized programs of education;
- transition from the student's external motivation to internal moral willful regulation, etc.

Increasing the effectiveness of modern didactics and educational content in education, scientific development and practical justification of new ideas and technologies. In this case, the connection between various pedagogical systems and teaching technologies, the approbation of new forms of the state education system in practice, and the application of pedagogical systems of the past in the current conditions are important.

Before the emergence of pedagogical technology, the rule of sufficiently efficient design of the educational process was not developed within the framework of the educational system, where, among other issues, complex devices and processes are studied. Pedagogical technology fills this gap, leaving ample room for the creative approach of the pedagogue to the planned educational process.

The unique aspect of pedagogical technology is that it is designed and implemented in the educational process to achieve educational goals. The

technological approach, first of all, is not superficial, but is expressed in a constructive, instructive scheme that allows the realization of the planned result.

Goal orientation, diagnostic examination of the results of the process, division of education into separate teaching episodes, all such aspects of the educational process make it possible to embody the idea of the educational redevelopment cycle today.

It mainly includes:

- setting a common goal in education;
- transition from a general goal to a specific goal;
- preliminary (diagnostic) assessment of students' knowledge levels;
- set of educational tasks to be performed (at this stage, it should be possible to make corrections to the educational process immediately based on feedback);
- evaluation of the result.

The standard of complete standardization of learning objectives can be as follows:

- a) high, but not absolute:
- b) absolute.

In the first case, due to the complexity of the goal, it does not allow to turn it into a type of fully observable behavior, the cycle is not completely reproduced.

In the second case, work is carried out with the reproductive type of education, which is a conveyor process.

At the planning stage of organizing the educational process on the basis of pedagogical technology, leading pedagogic scientists, methodist teachers are required to be highly qualified when developing methodical materials based on the rules and principles of pedagogical technology. When the materials are ready, the pedagogue mainly performs organizational and consultative tasks (with the possibility of creative additions).

At all stages of the educational process, it is possible to observe that the main technological aspect of the entire system is oriented to the final results of the educational process.

In general, pedagogical technology includes:

- development of identified educational goals;
- taxonomy of learning objectives;
- turning educational goals into control (test) assignments;
- ways to achieve the goal;
- assessment of achieved educational goals.

The main way to understand pedagogical technology is to focus on clearly defined goals, to establish regular interaction with the learner. Interaction forms the basis of pedagogical technology and covers the entire educational process. The teacher (pedagogue) sets a goal for the students to understand and master the content of the educational material, acquire certain knowledge and learn to apply it to practice. But what does mastering, understanding, and application mean? How does a teacher (pedagogue) know that he has achieved his goal?

Only when there are clear means of knowing whether the pedagogical goal has been achieved or not, the teacher (pedagogue) can be sure that his work is effective and the chosen methods are appropriate, or, on the contrary, ineffective.

According to M.V. Klarin, the typical methods of setting goals by teachers are as follows:

1. Setting the goal based on the plan of the educational material.
2. Determination of the goal through the activities of the teacher (pedagogue).
3. Setting educational goals through internal processes and laws of intellectual, emotional, personal development of the student.

Determining the purpose of education and the content of education through the activity of a teacher (pedagogue) or student-student does not allow to have a clear impression of the expected results in education. Regarding these results, it can be observed that the activity of students is manifested only externally. This is a very simple and ineffective way to achieve the goal.

In developed countries, it is customary to set goals for students and teachers (pedagogues) separately. This is logically correct, because the teaching process is a cooperative activity of the pedagogue and the pupil-student.

In this case, the goals are set based on the activities of the teacher (pedagogue) (teaching, explaining, showing, telling, etc.), and the results expressed in the character of the student are called the tasks of education. In this sense, educational tasks mean what the student can know or do at the end of the training.

In general, in order to be able to measure, define and repeat the tasks in the educational process, it is necessary to know the criteria for achieving each goal, that is, the educational goal should be set in such a way that it is clear about its achievement. be able to draw a conclusion.

The basis of innovative approaches to education is the content of technological, systematic and creative research approaches, that is, the student is placed at the center of education.

Comparative analysis of approaches to education.

Verbal-visual instructional explanation (traditional)	Technological	Research
Transfer of information from teacher to student.	Designing the educational process using a systematic approach.	Solving problems.
Unclear educational goals.	Clarify educational goals as much as possible.	Educational research.
Presentation of ready knowledge.	Implementation of education through the student's activity (movement).	Connection between subjects.
<p>The priority organizational forms of the educational process are conversation, story.</p> <p>Voluntary retention of information.</p> <p>Constantly giving permission to remember, consolidate and enrich (collect) information.</p> <p>The stages of knowledge consist of some subjects that are not sufficiently connected to a single system.</p> <p>The trainings are (mostly) academic in nature and are not sufficiently connected with the future work of specialists.</p>	<p>Correcting the educational process through feedback.</p> <p>Formative and final assessment.</p> <p>Regulatory control (testing).</p> <p>Full mastery of knowledge and skills.</p> <p>Guaranteed to achieve planned results.</p> <p>Effectiveness of education.</p>	<p>Making hypotheses and testing them.</p> <p>Collection of materials, modeling, experiment.</p> <p>Reflexive, critical, creative thinking.</p> <p>A lot of moderation, evidence.</p> <p>Making decisions.</p> <p>Role playing game.</p> <p>Acceptance of news, morality, spirituality, social responsibility. to be able to increase intellectuality.</p> <p>Receptivity to news.</p>

In pedagogy, a technological approach and a research-research approach are necessary. Each approach has its own area of application. Therefore, it is appropriate to combine them optimally in organizing the educational process. As mentioned above, currently developed countries have developed models of pedagogical technologies for different levels of education, including productive (productive) and search-creative models.

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